

FOUR MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS IN TEACHING

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Abstract

Everyone knows that victory in battle is forged in peacetime. At the same time, the subunit's readiness for skillful and resolute actions in the conditions of modern combat is not limited to combat training alone. High combat readiness, combat readiness, training and discipline are the result of the whole complex of types and activities of units in peacetime. Therefore, it is far from accidental that one of the most important tasks facing the troops is the task aimed at improving the management of the daily activities of units.

Key words: Planning, management, management, unity, society, team.

Management is a purposeful and constant process of influence of the subject of management on the object of management. Various phenomena and processes act as an object of control: a person, a team, a social community, mechanisms, technological processes, apparatuses.

The following types of management are distinguished:

- Mechanical, technical management (management of equipment, machines, technological processes).
- Natural management (management of vital processes of living organisms).
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- Social management (management of social processes, people and organizations).

Signs of management:

- Mandatory quality of an integral organized system.
- The presence of mandatory elements: the subject of management and the object of management.
- A certain focus, the achievement of the goal (managerial result).
- Serves the interests of the interaction of the main elements.
- It is provided by a system of certain means.

Thus, management in the most general sense of the word is understood as the organized activity of a person or a group of people aimed at achieving a given goal by a certain team. Subunit management consists in the purposeful activity of commanders in maintaining a constant high combat readiness of subunits,

preparing them for combat and leading them in the performance of assigned tasks. Success in combat in most cases depends on the quality of management. The experience of wars shows that skillful leadership of troops made it possible to crush the enemy with the least losses and achieve victory in a short time.

But it is impossible to achieve the goal without such functions as planning, organization, motivation and control. The first major function of management is planning. At the beginning of the journey, you need to set goals that need to be achieved. After the set goals, the path of movement and methods for the implementation of the tasks set are visible. Management of a unit and education of discipline is impossible without specifically formulated goals. Planning - its essence lies in the fact that the management defines strategic goals and objectives, makes strategic and operational decisions on them, determines the methods and terms for achieving the planned, the necessary material and labor reserves and resources, performers and responsible persons. Good planning of daily activities implies the type of purpose of the organization and the specific actions of the members of this organization.

Planning implies the formulation of the following questions:

- Determining the strength of the organization, its location at the present time.
- Defining a checkpoint and planning activities to achieve goals.
- The distribution of powers in the organization among its members to achieve the goals.

Planning the daily activities of departments is a creative and responsible task of management, which is a cyclical event, because after achieving the set goals, the organization continues to exist. Its essence lies in the fact that, in accordance with the requirements of the governing documents, the instructions of senior commanders, the prevailing situation and the capabilities of the units, determine the procedure and methods for solving the task with the least expenditure of effort, money and time. Practically all staff officials participate in the preparation of data for decision-making, and only the commander makes the decision and bears personal responsibility for it.

There are several types of planning:

1. Strategic planning is focused on developing a general strategy and setting the main goals, managing strategically important factors of activity, identifying

strategic ones, etc. The main goal of strategic planning is to create the potential for survival in the external and internal environment

2. Tactical planning involves justification tasks and means necessary to achieve the strategic goals.
3. Operational scheduling is a choice of means for solving problems that are defined by higher management, and are also traditional. The main task of this planning is to specify the indicators of the tactical plan in order to organize daily systematic and rhythmic work.
4. Centralized planning provides for the establishment by a higher management body of a subordinate enterprise of planned indicators of natural volumes of production, the range and timing of delivery of goods, and others that are mandatory for it.
5. Short-term (current) planning is carried out for a period of up to one year, including semi-annual, quarterly, monthly, weekly and daily planning.
6. Operational planning is a choice of means for solving problems that are defined by higher management, and are also traditional for the enterprise. Such planning is usually short term. Operational plans are made for a month, a day and a shift.
7. There are three scheduling methods: serial, parallel, and serial-parallel. As a rule, their implementation is based on a network or program-target planning method. The method is a specific system: for each planned goal and task, there is its own program of action.

Planning principles:

1. Unity.
2. Continuity.
3. Flexibility.
4. Accuracy.

Participation The principle of unity suggests that planning is systemic; this means unity of purpose for both the vertical management hierarchy and horizontal connections. The principle of participation is considered in close connection with the principle of unity. It means that a citizen, regardless of the function occupied and performed, becomes a participant in the planned activity.

The principle of continuity means that the planning process in time must be continuous based on the following prerequisites:

- changes in the external environment may be unpredictable and require adjustments to the plan;

– it is not always possible to foresee a change in the internal sphere.

The principle of flexibility lies in the need to provide for certain production reserves when drawing up plans. The amount of reserves depends on the level of professional competence. They should be sufficient to achieve the goal, not overestimated or underestimated. The principle of accuracy is associated with the concept of "efficiency" of the plan and the principle of flexibility, that is, plans should be as close as possible to the existing capabilities of the enterprise. Planning the daily activities of the unit plays a particularly important role in today's conditions, when tasks increase significantly and become more complicated, it is necessary to revise plans to maintain the relevance of actions. The planning function involves the rational distribution of human and material resources to complete the task, the definition of a logical sequence of actions, the development of plan documents, its coordination and approval.

The plan is the main guiding document for the officer, along with the order, which indicates the time of work, place of work and performers. The organization of the activity of the unit is a management function that ensures the transition of the unit from the existing state to the planned state. This function includes the distribution of work among the department, the grouping of tasks into logical blocks, the creation of departments and the coordination of their work. In turn, the organization is necessary to achieve the goals and implement the plans. For enhanced implementation of the plan, the manager needs to distribute tasks among human resources. The organization of management is a set of actions leading to the formation and improvement of the relationship between the parts of the whole, which makes it possible to realize the goals of management. The organization is seen as an algorithm that can determine the sequence of work in the modernization of the management process. The organization as a function of management is aimed at putting the planned plans and decisions into practice. Organization as a function is the coordination of tasks and relationships between people, as well as the process of creating structure. In nature, there are two aspects of the organizational process: the creation of a command structure for military units and the distribution of authority among subordinates. Authority is a limited right of an official to use the resources of the unit and manage people. In turn, responsibility cannot be delegated, since it is the duty of a soldier to fulfill the tasks set by the chief and be responsible for their implementation. Relationships are built on trust.

The leader must trust his subordinates, but at the same time soberly assess their capabilities, organize and distribute tasks among the members of the unit in such a way that they fully and efficiently perform the work assigned to them. The direct function of the organization lies in the commander's ability to link the will and actions of military personnel in relation to the most frequent actions and the ability to create the greatest independence in subunits. But for the most effective organization, you need the right motivation. Motivation of the activities of units is a management function that provides for the creation of an internal incentive for the unit to act in order to achieve the goals set for the unit in accordance with the duties delegated to them and according to the plans. Motivation is the way to effective management of a person. Motivation is a set of factors that induce a person to certain actions, set the boundaries and forms of activity and give a guide to achieving certain goals. Motive is the force that motivates a person to act. The motive entirely depends on the factors acting on the person, as well as the actions of others. In psychology, the concept of motive is deciphered as incentives for activity related to the satisfaction of the needs of the subject; perceived reason underlying the choice of actions and actions of the individual. There is such a thing as a motivational structure. It means something other than the basis of actions carried out by a person. This structure can change under certain conditions, for example, during education. Motivation itself is a process of influencing a person with the aim of inducing him to certain actions. Motivation is the basis of human management.

Thus, the purpose of control is to implement feedback in the control system of the day-to-day activities of troops, to identify deviations and shortcomings in the implementation of its goals and objectives, and to take measures to ensure their achievement. Monitoring the state of combat readiness and the progress of tasks is divided into three types: current, periodic, final. Current control is a daily procedure that exists to stimulate the activity of subordinates. Periodic control is carried out by commanders and chiefs in order to check the level of training in units and subunits. The final control is carried out by the decision of senior commanders in order to check the state of combat readiness of subunits, units and formations. This type of control is carried out, as a rule, at the end of the training period. In the course of control, the commander must identify shortcomings, which, upon completion of the inspection, are eliminated in a planned manner. Managing the day-to-day activities of troops is, first of all, managing people.

Therefore, all control is completely dependent on the personal qualities of the commander and officials of the control bodies. Professional training, confidence in the correctness of actions, high exactingness and trust allow the commander to subjugate large teams to his will, to mobilize their physical, intellectual and spiritual forces to the maximum for the successful completion of the assigned tasks. The implementation of all these principles is impossible without a high level of organizational skills, high-quality planning and control in solving tasks, as well as proper motivation of subordinates.

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